

THE PECULIARITIES OF POLITENESS IN THE LINGUISTIC CULTURE OF THE TURKMEN AND JAPANESE PEOPLES

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To understand people from different cultures, it is not enough to study their psychology. The main thing is to understand how they perceive the outside world. A prime example of this is the fact that there are several levels of Japanese proficiency. Politeness is a form of communication between people. In a polite conversation, appropriate words are used depending on the level, such as “commanding - lower”, “senior - junior”, “friends - strangers” [1]. For example, just look at the words used to express gratitude in Japanese. The words in Turkmen language like as: "sag boluň" and "minnetdar", used in the usual sense for all, are expressed differently in Japanese depending on the position of the interlocutor in society, the service rendered to them and the attention rendered. The word arigato is often used to express gratitude when a person refers to his or her family and children.

In general, there are dozens of expressions of gratitude in Japanese. This means that in the Japanese picture of the world, politeness manifests itself in different ways depending on the position of person, place in society, age kinship. Politeness is taught from childhood. The Japanese phrase "reigi tadashii" does not have a Russian translation. In a large Russian-Japanese dictionary [2], this phrase is translated as "любезный", but the words in Japanese and Russian differ in semantics and meaning. The meaning of this word can be understood by dividing it into two parts. The word "reigi" means "etiquette", "rules of conduct". The word "tadashii" means "correct", "lawful" [3]. Based on these words, the phrase "reigi tadashii" fully corresponds to the meaning of the word "edep" in the Turkmen language. Thus, to be polite, to behave correctly in society are characteristics of the Turkmen and Japanese peoples. These characteristics reveal the similarity of cultural values of both nations.

In Japan, it is considered impolite to express your emotions such as happiness, sadness, or fear in the presence of strangers. In the Japanese mentality, it is considered wrong to agree or disagree. They are obvious in Japanese. For example, the sentence 気にしてありませんから (“ki ni shite arimasen kara”) means “I can’t accept it”. This can be translated into Turkmen as "Men gównämok" or "Men garşy". There is no definite "no" in Japanese. This word is used only in the family or among close relatives and friends. The Japanese avoid saying "no" when talking to strangers. The word いいえ means "no" and is rarely used [4]. Although the Japanese people know that the interlocutor feels that they do not agree with them, without saying a clear "no", they leave the interlocutor with hope and scope for working together in the future. This shows the main national character of the Japanese politeness.

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